

PECULIARITIES OF FINANCIAL ACCOUNTING IN ECONOMY

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Annotation: This article deals with important facts about financial accounting, its features in economy today. Moreover, special accounting terms and their analysis are given.

Key words: *business transactions, “running totals”, revenue, Cash, credit cards, expense categories, business engaging, service-oriented businesses.*

Accounting may be defined as the process of analyzing, classifying, recording, summarizing, and interpreting business transactions. One of the key aspects of the process is keeping “running totals” of “things.” Examples of items a business might keep track of include the amount of cash the business currently has, what a company has paid for utilities for the month, the amount of money it owes, its income for the entire year, and the total cost of all the equipment it has purchased. You want to always have these running totals up to date so they are readily available to you when you need the information. It is similar to checking what your cash balance in the bank is when deciding if you have enough money to make a purchase with your debit card. There are many items that businesses keep records of. Each of these accounts fall into one of five categories.

1. Assets: Anything of value that a business owns
2. Liabilities: Debts that a business owes; claims on assets by outsiders
3. Stockholders’ equity: Worth of the owners of a business; claims on assets by the owners
4. Revenue: Income that results when a business operates and generates

sales

5. Expenses: Costs associated with earning revenue Different accounts fall into different categories.

Cash is an account that falls in the asset category[1]. The Cash account keeps track of the amount of money a business has. Checks, money orders, and debit and credit cards are considered to be cash. Other than Cash, we will begin by covering accounts that fall into the revenue and expense categories. Revenue is income that results from a business engaging in the activities that it is set up to do. For example, a computer technician earns revenue when they repairs a computer for a customer. If the same computer technician sells a van that they no longer needs for his business, it is not considered revenue. Fees Earned is an account name commonly used to record income generated from providing a service. In a service business, customers buy expertise, advice, action, or an experience but do not purchase a physical product. Consultants, dry cleaners, airlines, attorneys, and repair shops are service-oriented businesses. The Fees Earned account falls into the revenue category. Expenses are bills and other costs a business must pay in order for it to operate and earn revenue. As the adage goes, “It takes money to make money.” Expense accounts differ from business to business, depending on individual company needs.

Financial statements are key goals of the accounting process. In order to prepare them at the end of an accounting period, individual financial transactions must be analyzed, classified, and recorded all throughout the period. This initially takes place in a record book called the journal, where financial events called transactions are recorded as they happen, in chronological order. When a transaction occurs, two or more accounts are affected[2]. There is also a dollar amount associated with each of the accounts. Determining which accounts are impacted, and by how much, is the first step in making a journal entry.

The total of all the debit balances in a company’s ledger accounts must

always equal the total of all the credit balances. A trial balance is a list of all a business's accounts and its current ledger balances (copied over from the ledger accounts). A trial balance may be generated at any time to test whether total debits equals total credits. It is simply a worksheet to check for accuracy before preparing financial statements. If both of the Total columns do not equal, there is an error that must be found and corrected. The goal of journalizing, posting to the ledgers, and preparing the trial balance is to gather the information necessary to produce the financial statements. The time period concept requires companies produce the financial statements on a regular basis over the same time interval, such as a month or year. Most of the amounts on these statements are copied directly from the trial balance, and then appropriate calculations and summary amounts are also displayed.

The net income from a business's operations for a period of time is so important to business people and investors that one financial statement—the income statement—is dedicated to showing what that amount is and how it was determined. The income statement is a report that lists and summarizes revenue, expense, and net income information for a period of time, usually a month or a year. It is based on the following equation: $\text{Revenue} - \text{Expenses} = \text{Net income (or Net loss)}$. Revenue is shown first; a list of expenses follows, and their total is subtracted from revenue. If the difference is positive, there is a profit, or net income. If the difference is negative, there is a net loss that is typically presented in parentheses as a negative number. The income statement answers a business's most important question: How much profit is it making? It is limited to a specific period of time (month or year) from beginning to end. The income statement relies on the matching principle in that it only reports revenue and expenses in a specified window of time. It does not include any revenue or expenses from before or after that block of time.

Accounting is practiced under a guideline called the time period

assumption, which allows the ongoing activities of a business to be divided up into periods of a year, quarter, month, or other increment of time. The precise time period covered is included in the headings of the income statement, the retained earnings statement, and the statement of cash flows[3]. Therefore, the accounting process is cyclical. A cycle is a period of time in which a series of accounting activities are performed. As was just stated, the typical accounting cycle is a year, a month, or perhaps a quarter. Once the current cycle is completed, the same recording and reporting activities are then repeated in the next period of time of equal length. In accounting, journalizing and posting transactions to the ledgers are done every day in the cycle. Financial statements are typically prepared only on the last day of the cycle. Once the financial statements are complete, the process continues on into the next accounting period, where again the financial statements are the goal of the recordkeeping process. The financial statements are the goal of all that is done in the accounting cycle. However, there are some steps that need to be taken once those reports are completed to set up the ledgers for the next cycle. These steps involve closing entries. Closing entries are special journal entries made at the end of the accounting period (month or year) after the financial statements are prepared but before the first transaction in the next month is recorded in the journal.

The purpose of closing entries is to set the balances of income statement accounts back to zero so you can start fresh and begin accumulating new balances for the next month. This process ensures that the balances on the second month's income statement do not include amounts from transactions in the first month. Profit at the end of the accounting period is transferred into a new account called Retained Earnings when the revenue and expense accounts are closed out. The Retained Earnings account is only used for closing entries. Closing entries transfer the balances from the revenue and expense accounts into Retained Earnings in preparation for the new month. Retained Earnings is an account where

profit is “stored.” Think of the retained earnings balance as “accumulated profit,” or all the net income that the business has ever generated since it began operations. Assume a business’s accounting period is a month. For the first month in which the business operates, the beginning retained earnings balance is zero since there were no previous periods and therefore no previous profits. At the end of the first month, the retained earnings balance equals the net income for the month[4]. After the first month, when closing entries for the current month are journalized and posted, the additional net income for the next month is added to any net income already in Retained Earnings from previous months. Since $\text{Revenue} - \text{Expenses} = \text{Net Income}$, moving revenue and expense balances into Retained Earnings is the same as moving the net income.

To sum up all given facts above, Accounting is a system meant for measuring business activities, processing of information into reports and making the findings available to decision-makers. The documents, which communicate these findings about the performance of an organisation in monetary terms, are called financial statements. Usually, accounting is understood as the Language of Business. However, a business may have a lot of aspects which may not be of financial nature. As such, a better way to understand accounting could be to call it The Language of Financial Decisions. The better the understanding of the language, the better is the management of financial aspects of living. Many aspects of our lives are based on accounting, personal financial planning, investments, income-tax, loans, etc. We have different roles to perform in life-the role of a student, of a family head, of a manager, of an investor, etc. The knowledge of accounting is an added advantage in performing different roles. However, we shall limit our scope of discussion to a business organisation and the various financial aspects of such an organisation.

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